

JIGSAW STRATEGY TO TEACHING IPER STUDENTS

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Abstract. The jigsaw method was originally developed by Elliot Aronson in 1970 in Austin Texas. As cooperative learning technique, it has been studied by members of researches at different levels and subjects.

Key words: jigsaw, IPER students, cooperative learning, small group

There have been several modifications introduced in jigsaw strategy. In the original jigsaw each student of the group was given different material. Then all IPER students who have the same part of material gathered to form expert group. In this expert group the students discuss until they master the material. After that they return to their original group to explain the others about the materials. As suggested by Slavin in 1978 that jigsaw attaches more importance member belongs two different group, the home group and jigsaw group. At the beginning IPER students gather in their home group and each member of this home group is assigned to a part of material which they will have to learn as an expert. Jigsaw promotes to importance of self-esteem, intrinsic motivation, cooperative learning and developing student's strategies to construct meaning. most importantly jigsaw technique focus on the communicative process of language learning. The group task that follows individual peer teaching promotes discussion problem solving, and learning. Jigsaw encouraging cooperation and active learning and promotes valuing all students' contributions. Jigsaw can be an efficient cooperative learning strategy.

Johnson and Holubec state that there are five principles of jigsaw strategy;

1. Positive interdependence. In this principle each student should do some effort for the group success by making unique contribution to the joint effort;
2. Face to face primitive interaction. here is each group members should explain orally how to master the material or solve the problem, teaching the others, check other member understands discuss concept and link the present learning with the past one;
3. Individual accountability for the group achievement. The size of the

group should be small, because small group enhance greater individual accountability. Later the teacher should test the students randomly by asking one of the IPER students to present their group orally.

4. Interpersonal skills. This skill is an important part in achieving the success of jigsaw learning in class. This social skill includes decision making leadership, trust building communication and conflict management.

5. Group processing. In this process each group should discuss how well they achieve in their goals and maintain effective working relationship. Besides, they should discuss what actions are helpful and what behavior needs to continue or change.

Jigsaw is a strategy that emphasizes cooperative learning by providing IPER students an opportunity to actively help each other build comprehension. Use this technique to assign IPER students to reading groups composed of varying skill levels. Each group member is responsible for becoming an “expert” on one section of the assigned material and then “teaching” it to the other members of them.

Teachers can use the following steps when developing the jigsaw strategy for a class: Introduce the technique and the topic to be studied; Assign each student to a “home group” of 3-5 IPER students who reflect a range of reading abilities; Determine a set of reading selections and assign one selection to each student; Create “expert groups” that consist of students across “home groups” who will read the same selection; Give all IPER students a framework for managing their time on the various parts of the jigsaw task; Provide key questions to help the “expert groups” gather information in their particular area; Provide materials and resources necessary for all students to learn about their topics and become “experts”; Discuss the rules for reconvening into “home groups” and provide guidelines as each “expert” reports the information learned; Prepare a summary chart or graphic organizer for each “home group” as a guide for organizing the experts’ information report.; Remind IPER students that “home group” members are responsible to learn all content from the another.

It is important that IPER students have experience with small group learning skills before participating in the jigsaw strategy. It’s also important that the reading material assigned is at appropriate instructional levels.

IPER students are directed to read the selection of text assigned to them. When the reading has been completed, the IPER students meet for approximately 20 minutes with others assigned to the same topic. They discuss

the material, identify the most important learning points, and return to their “home groups” to instruct the others about information in which they have become an expert. Each student takes turns teaching what he or she has learned to the other home group members. During this process teachers should:

Circulate to ensure that groups are on task and managing their work well;

Ask groups to stop and think about how they are checking for everyone’s understanding and ensuring that everyone’s voice is heard;

Monitor the comprehension of the group members asking questions and rephrasing information until it’s clear that all group members understand the points.

If appropriate, have IPER students fill out a graphic organizer in the home group to gather all the information presented by each expert. Home groups then present results to the entire class, or they may participate in some assessment activity. Teachers may assign a team grade based upon academic and cooperative performance. This method encourages cooperative learning among IPER students. It helps to improve listening, communication, and problem solving skills.

Jigsaw Activity

Advantages and disadvantages of jigsaw method. There are some advantages of jigsaw method. This method helps the IPER students in learning the content of the subject the text, because the IPER students have practice in peer teaching, which requires that they understand the material at a deeper

level than IPER students typically do when simply task to produce on an exam. It has a strong effect on attitude to learning and social relationship among IPER students in group, because each student has a chance to contribute meaningfully to discussion, something that is difficult to achieve in group discussion. Each student develops an expertise and has something important to contribute share information

It enables the IPER students to understand the text because students require to prepare in their answering specific question in order to insure adequate IPER students' preparation, IPER students have a specific task that tasks IPER students to plan how they will teach that they have learn. So members of the group have to work together in order to establish a common goal. Each member is interdependent on each other. Cooperation and communication and necessary because no one can success member contributes. IPER students have the opportunity to teach themselves. Instead of having material presented them. The technique fosters depth of understanding. Each student has practiced it in self-teaching, which is the most valuable of the entire skill teacher can help them learn. IPER students can practice in peer teaching, which requires that they understand the material at deeper level than student typically do when simply asked to produce an exam. IPER students become more fluent in use of English. Each IPER students has a chance to contribute meaningfully to discussion that is difficult to achieve in large group discussion. Each student develops an expertise and has something important to contribute. Asking each group to discuss a follow up question after individual presentation fosters real discussions.

Disadvantages of jigsaw method. There are some disadvantages of jigsaw method. This method requires long time to prepare IPER students to be assigned who to work in groups. Because they are heterogenic members that must learn how to work in groups and out needed by all other participants to complete the given task. But there is one leader in their member who dominance unsuccessful group. If they cannot work in group, they cannot get sufficient information. It requires sometime to make group which is heterogeneity in their ability, because there is one student as a leader, who is responsible for being fair and spreading participation evenly and order to reduce a problem in their group, be responsible in their information. Because IPER students work with other individuals from other groups working on the same segment on the report. So that IPER students that do possible to the other group and to add the group,

they will be mention bad member and this event show that heterogeneity members.

IPER students have the opportunity to teach themselves. Instead of having material presented them. The technique fosters depth of understanding. It requires long time to arrange the seating, because in reading jigsaw activity the teacher needs to float from group to group in order to observe the process.

Techniques for using jigsaw method. The following two jigsaw examples lie at opposite ends of the spectrum in terms of length and complexity and also illustrate just how versatile the jigsaw technique is. Following these two examples, you will find examples of many different types of jigsaws that can be adopted, adapted or simply serve as catalysts for your own thinking.

The long: Discovering plate boundaries

One of the best known and most widely used jigsaw activities for geoscience courses is the Discovering Plate Boundaries exercise developed by Dale Sawyer. The exercise is built around four global data maps: 1) earthquake location and depth, 2) location of recent volcanic activity, 3) seafloor age, and 4) topography and bathymetry.

Each team works with one of the global data maps and determines where they would put the plate boundaries based on the data that they have. For a large class, Dale breaks each data-type team into sub-teams that focus on only one particular plate or group of plates.

After re-forming into mixed groups, each student teaches the others in the group about what his/her data set suggests about plate boundary locations.

The group task is then to combine the different data sets and work together as a group to determine where plate boundaries lie and why.

This jigsaw is an effective way for students to explore plate boundaries based on observations that they can make. The exercise takes three one-hour classes or one three-hour lab to complete. You can find the full exercise, data sets, and a Journal of Geoscience Education article about the activity at the link above.

The short: Igneous rock classification

At the opposite end of the complexity spectrum, is a very simple, but effective jigsaw on igneous rock classification developed for a large introductory geology course. As IPER students enter the auditorium, they each pick up one rock from a box of samples by the classroom door. The box contains samples of granite, gabbro, and basalt. The instructor asks students to study their rock

samples individually and write down all the observations they can make about them. The task is simple enough to use in a large class without having to check on each student's preparation. After giving IPER students several minutes to study their rocks, the instructor asks the IPER students to make groups of three so that each group has three different rock types. IPER students teach each other what they saw in their own rocks, and the group then compares rocks, noting similarities and differences. The instructor then asks groups what they have noted in their rocks and writes down responses on the board.

IPER students make all of the observations that one might expect them to make about color, grain size, and texture, providing an engaging base for the instructor to introduce igneous rock classification. Although the jigsaw assignment takes time in class, the instructor does not need to spend as much time lecturing about igneous rock classification. If planned well, the overall time committed to using this jigsaw during class is comparable to that of lecturing about the topic. And the IPER students will retain a mental image of these three rock types. Jigsaws using graphs, formulas, and equations. Short jigsaws during class that help students learn to plot data, interpret graphs, and use formulas and equations are easy to construct and valuable for students. The team assignment gives students an opportunity to grapple with a graph or equation and master it well enough to explain it. One effective way to have teams prepare is to have team members create their own concept sketches of the graph or equation. A concept sketch has a central graphic (e.g., a graph or an equation) that is concisely annotated with short statements (not just labels) that describe a student's understanding of the elements shown in the central graphic. A subsequent group task comparing team assignments provides students an opportunity to explore, for example, how a graph varies with different data inputs, how the terms in an equation influence the output, how different portrayals of the same data might result in different interpretations, and so on. Jigsaw is a terrific way to have students examine and analyze unique but related objects. Each student benefits not only from individual in-depth analysis but also from the picture that the groups put together by exploring a range of examples. Jigsaw is particularly useful if you have a great collection of objects, pictures, images, or samples, but you don't have enough copies for each student to work with identical ones. Just remember that this works best if you don't need student to know each example equally well. On many occasions, we'd like IPER students not only to analyze a given data set but also to work with several other examples to see how they relate to one another, vary from one another, or can be

combined to make a complete picture. Commonly, however, there's not enough time for students to do a complete analysis of several data sets, or it would be either repetitive or too time-consuming to have them do more than one. The jigsaw technique is a great technique to allow students to spend time analyzing one data set in depth, learn about others in less depth from a peer, and put together a complete picture that is not clear from only one data set. The team data analysis portion of the jigsaw could be done outside of class, in a lab session, or during class.

Jigsaws for reading in the literature. One of the problems with assigning outside reading in preparation for a class discussion is that, if everyone does the reading and comes adequately prepared, it's hard to "discuss the reading" during class in an interesting way. The literature is also typically difficult for undergraduates to read, and assigning multiple articles to achieve either breadth or depth might not be desirable. Jigsaw offers an interesting way around both problems by having teams of students reading different but related articles and achieving depth and breadth in mixed groups. The key involves selecting related articles and helping students prepare adequately. Telling IPER students to "do the reading and come prepared to teach it" is typically not very successful. Having students prepare written answers to guiding questions or create concept sketches of key figures can help students prepare well for class. During peer teaching, having students' role play the sounds silly but is remarkably effective for changing the tone in mixed groups from classroom to quasi-professional.

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can say jigsaw method helps build comprehension, encourages cooperative learning among students and helps improve listening, communication, and problem-solving skills. Just as in a jigsaw puzzle, each piece--each student's part is essential for the completion and full understanding of the final product. If each student's participation is essential, then each student is essential.

And that is exactly what makes this strategy so effective. The jigsaw strategy is a remarkably efficient way to learn the material. More importantly, the jigsaw process encourages listening, engagement, and empathy by giving each member of the group an essential part to play in the academic activity. Group members must work together as a team to accomplish a common goal each person depends on all the others. No student can succeed completely unless everyone works well together as a team. Of all the cooperative learning strategies, I think that the jigsaw technique is the most effective. After all, when IPER students

learn something well enough that they can teach it to others, they have truly mastered the material. There is a corollary benefit as well students working as a team, with each team member contributing to the overall success of the group, learn a vital real-life lesson. As you know, no matter how your kids will eventually be employed, they will always be part of a team effort. And, the jigsaw strategy allows them to hone their cooperative and competitive skills in an arena far removed from the athletic field. It would be very effective if teachers implement this method correctly in lessons. I recommend this method as an interactive method.

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